

Experimental and Discussion

Cobalt chloride and nickel chloride used were of B.D.H. A.R. specifications. All other chemicals and reagent used were of A.R. specifications and chemically pure. The spectrophotometric measurements were carried out with a quartz spectrophotometer, Beckmann model D.U. and the *pH* of the solutions were measured with Philips *pH* meter. P.R. 9400. All the solutions were kept in a thermostat bath and the measurements were carried out at $28^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$.

Synthesis of the Azo-dye: The above azo-dye have been synthesized by diazotising sulphanilic acid and then coupling the diazotised product with *p*-cresol. The dye was isolated as barium salt and the above dye was obtained by treating the barium salt with sodium sulphate solution. The azo dye was recrystallised with ethanol and its purity was tested by percentage estimation of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur.

Stoichiometry of the Chelates: Vosburgh and Cooper method¹, Job's method of continuous variation² and mole ratio method³ were used to determine the stoichiometry of the chelates with the help of spectrophotometer at *pH* range 6.5 to 7.0 maintained with the help of 0.1*M* HCl. The data have been shown in Figures 1 to 4. Figures clearly indicate that in the chelates the ratio of metal and ligand is 1 : 1.

Stability Constants of the Chelates: Stability constants of the chelates have been calculated using Job's method with non-equimolar solutions and the values obtained are 8.237×10^2 and 1.139×10^3 for cobalt and nickel chelate respectively. The above values are confirmed by the mole ration method⁴ also.

The above low stability constant values of cobalt than nickel are in natural order of stability *i.e.*, the stability constant values vary in the order $Mn^{2+} < Fe^{2+} < Co^{2+} < Ni^{2+} < Cu^{2+}$. This order is relatively consistent with the charge to radius concept, since the radii of the ions vary in the order $Mn^{2+} > Fe^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Ni^{2+}$.

Discussion and Formula: The 1 : 1 complex clearly indicates that the ligand is bidentate and the OH group ortho to azo group is holding the metal ion. The metal is coordinated with two molecules of water also. Thus the possible formula is $(ML_2 \cdot 2H_2O) Na$, where M stands for metal, cobalt and nickel and L is the ligand under study.

References

1. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
2. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113; *Chem. Abs.*, 1928, **22**, 2120.
3. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
4. H. MCCONNELL and N. DAVIDSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3164.

Studies on N-Substituted Salicylhydroxamic Acids as Metal Complexing Ligands. Part VII. $UO_2(II)$ Chelates of N-Methyl Salicylhydroxamic Acid

NRIPENDRA NATH GHOSH & ARUNA MUKHERJEE

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory, University College of Science, Calcutta-9

Manuscript received 30 January 1973; revised 17 July 1973; accepted 18 July 1973

N-METHYLSALICYLHYDROXAMIC acid (RH_2) gives different coloured solutions with $UO_2(II)$ with changes in *pH* values indicating the existence of a number of $UO_2(II)$ complexes in solution. Therefore in order to find out the composition of various $UO_2(II)$ complexes present in the solution, Job's method of continuous variation¹ has been undertaken employing colour as the index property.

Experimental

In the preparation of the solutions, double-distilled water was used. N-Methyl salicylhydroxamic acid was prepared in the laboratory and purified by recrystallisation². All other reagents used were either of A.R. quality or properly purified. Optical densities were measured with a Spectrophotometer (Hilger's UVISPEK) using 1 cm quartz cell against water. A Cambridge portable type *pH*-meter was employed for adjusting *pH* values.

In studying the formation of complexes by Job's method of continuous variation, all solutions were prepared in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol. First spectral curves were drawn for complexes formed at three different *pH* values. From the curves wavelengths 540 nm and 480 nm were selected for studying the formation of complexes by Job's method at three different *pH* values ≈ 2.0 , ≈ 4.5 and $\approx 5.8-6.0$. The differences of optical densities between the observed values and the calculated values were plotted against the corresponding composition. From the curves the existence of (1 : 1) complexes in solution has been observed at three different *pH* values.

Results and Discussion

By Job's method of continuous variation, two different complexes of $UO_2(II)$ with RH_2 are indicated. The reddish-brown complex at *pH* ≈ 2.0 and the yellow one at *pH* $\approx 5.8-6.0$, both have the same composition (1 : 1). It is known that diuranates are formed at *pH* ≈ 6.0 , therefore it may be suggested that the yellow complex at *pH* $\approx 5.8-6.0$, is a binuclear diuranate type compound—composition being (2 : 2). The composition of this complex by means of the method of proportional absorptivities³ has also been studied. The proportion of absorptivities A_2/A_1 can be determined at various *pH*-values, where A_2 and A_1 are the optical densities of the stronger and weaker solutions respectively at the

same λ and pH value. In (1:1) complexes these proportions are constant and in (2:2) complexes (or more polynuclear complexes) these proportions are variable. Data for the system $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})\text{-RH}_2$ are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. COMPOSITION OF COMPLEXES OF $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ AND RH_2 AT HIGHER pH VALUES

$$C_M = C_L = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ or } 1.0 \times 10^{-2}; C_M : C_L = 1 : 1$$

pH values	λ (nm)	A_2	A_1	A_2/A_1
5.8-6.0	480	0.550	0.185	2.97
4.5	480	0.297	0.129	2.30
5.8-6.0	540	0.218	0.055	3.78
4.5	540	0.141	0.047	3.00

From the data the composition of the complexes at higher pH-values appears to be (2:2) or more polynuclear. The compound having the composition (1:2) has been isolated in the solid state², but the existence of the *bis*-compound could not be proved in solution.

References

1. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **10**, 113.
2. N. N. GHOSH, A. MUKHERJEE (*nee* BHATTACHARYYA) and A. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 637.
3. B. BUDESINSKY, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1965, **209**, 379.

Infra-red Absorption at two Microns and Electron Spin Resonance Studies on some Coal-Tar Pitches

K. A. KINI

Till recently Head of Physical Chemistry Section, Warren Spring Laboratory, Stevenage, Hertfordshire, U.K.

Manuscript received 26 September 1972; revised 21 May 1973; accepted 24 July 1973

IN a previous paper, Walker and Baumbach¹ have drawn attention to the relation between background absorption at 2μ of coaltar pitches and their quinoline insoluble content. The authors concluded that background absorption at 2μ arises from the quinoline insoluble phase of the pitches. The absorption at 2μ was chosen, because Montgomery and Goodspeed² had shown previously that increased background at that wavelength could be correlated with increased compressive strength of electrodes prepared from the pitches. A fact that was recognised, but not taken into account by Walker and Baumbach¹ is the possible electronic absorption by the quinoline soluble portion of the pitch. The

availability of three pitches, with their quinoline soluble and insoluble fractions separated, enabled this possibility to be tested. Further, in this study, some electron spin resonance measurements have been made on the same pitches, and the quinoline soluble as well as the insoluble fractions of three of them.

The experimental procedure in the case of infra-red absorption was the same as previously¹, except that the material was ground to -200 U.S. sieve, and that 0.6 mg in the case of the original pitch (or its quinoline soluble fraction) or 0.15 mg of the quinoline fraction, as the case may be, was mixed with KBr to make a disc of weight 0.3 g. The discs, specially the ones containing the quinoline insoluble fraction, were transferred to the spectrometer immediately after preparation, because it was found that they developed opacity on keeping.

The electron spin resonance measurements were made on a home-built e.s.r. apparatus at a frequency of 9000 Mc/s, using DPPH as a standard. The pitches (0.03 g) were mixed with an equal quantity of silica (chromatographic grade) in order to eliminate any possible skin effect, although in a few cases tested, no evidence of the latter was found. Since oxygen was found to have a suppressing effect on the intensity, the samples were evacuated in high vacuum (10^{-5} mm. Hg.) overnight at room temperature. Since the purpose of the investigation was a study of the relative variation of e.s.r. parameters with the quinoline insoluble content of the pitches, the values obtained are more relative than absolute.

The infra-red spectrogram obtained for a typical pitch is shown in Fig. 1. The considerable absorption at 2μ has been ascribed by Walker¹ to electronic absorption by the quinoline soluble phase. However, since the absorption at 2μ was found to be constant for the three pitches examined, *viz.*, 5, 14 and 16, the absorption at 2μ of the whole pitches was corrected for the absorption by subtracting this constant amount from the total intensity. This procedure also takes care of any residual scattering. The corrected absorption is plotted against the quinoline insoluble content in Fig. 2.

It is seen that the relationship, observed previously, by Walker and Baumbach¹, is confirmed. Pitch 4 and 5, which were the exceptional pitches of the earlier investigation, still remain so. Investigation with the quinoline insoluble portion of pitches 14 and 16 (Table 1) shows that even in the quinoline insoluble portion, the absorption at 2μ is constant. This result is surprising in view of the opinion prevailing³ that there is a distribution of molecular weight in the quinoline insoluble fraction. Although the present evidence is by no means exhaustive, so far as background absorption is concerned, the quinoline insoluble fractions of normal pitches behave more or less identically.

The results of the present investigation, therefore, have added support to the previous conclusion that